

THE SOCIO-EDITORIAL NECESSITY OF DEVELOPING INFORMATION CULTURE AMONG STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the principles, methodological conditions, and factors influencing the development of students' information culture in the process of innovative education in the world education system, and introduces indicators for determining the level of development of students' information culture in the process of innovative education. The article discusses the approaches taken in higher education institutions of a number of countries, such as the USA, Russia, Bulgaria, Australia, South Korea, China, and Kazakhstan, to developing the information culture of the next generation, to developing students' complex knowledge and skills in the information field during higher education, to searching for innovative ways of applying them to practical activities, and to using software tools.*

Keywords: *interdisciplinary, information, culture, communication, problems. globalization, communication, technologies, technological, media.*

Introduction

In our rapidly developing country, modern society relies on information and knowledge. Currently, the rapid spread of media and various forms of information and communication technologies, as well as their influence on our personal, economic, political, and social life, cannot be denied. Therefore, for people to actively and effectively participate in the life of the information society, new knowledge, skills, and guidelines are necessary.

Literature Review and Methodology

The frequently used term “*literacy*” is now increasingly applied together with concepts such as “*digital,*” “*computer,*” “*visual,*” “*technological,*” “*communication,*” and, of course, “*media*” and “*information culture.*” In our country, comprehensive measures are being implemented to actively develop the digital economy and to widely introduce modern information and communication technologies across all sectors, especially in public administration and the education system.

In particular, priority projects are being carried out aimed at improving the e-government system, further developing the local market for software products and information technologies, establishing IT parks throughout the country, and ensuring the provision of qualified personnel for the sector. The adoption of Presidential Decree N. PD-6079 of May 10, 2020, “*On the approval and effective implementation of the Digital Uzbekistan – 2030 strategy*” has opened wide opportunities for development and extensive research in this field. One of the most urgent tasks is fostering students’ information culture.

Furthermore, in Presidential Decree N. PD-5712 of April 29, 2019, “*On the approval of the Concept for the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030*”, it is noted that although the state educational standards are based on a competency-based approach, teaching and assessment methods, as well as textbooks and other learning materials, are mainly aimed at memorizing and reproducing information. This, in turn, hinders the development

of critical thinking, the ability to independently search for and analyze information, and other important skills. The decree emphasizes that, taking into account the need to develop competencies and skills in independent information search and analysis, new state educational standards and general education programs that meet the requirements of the modern economy must be introduced.

Results and Discussion

Although the issues of developing information culture among higher education students have been theoretically addressed from various approaches, the rapid pace of globalization, the information society, and new directions in science and education strengthen the necessity of formulating modern requirements for the development of students' information culture.

This necessity can be summarized as follows. In particular:

Figure 1. The necessity of developing information culture

Information has become an integral part of society's life, and in the 21st century the possibilities for its transmission and reception are growing more effectively. The information space has turned into an important factor of scientific and social development. Social progress is reflected in the development of all spheres. In particular, education, as a part of social life, constantly mirrors the achievements of society.

Information culture is a part of general human culture and is an important element of modern information society culture. The logic of the research requires considering the definitions of "information," "culture," and "information system," as well as clarifying the essence of the concept of "students' information culture." [1]

While covering the topic in academic literature, it is clear to all of us that the concept of "information culture" has emerged relatively recently. The main reason for its emergence lies in the growing role of information, information technologies, and information activities in social life. However, from the very beginning, difficulties arose in defining this phenomenon, because the concept was formed on the basis of two universal notions - "information" and "culture" - which themselves had not been clearly interpreted in scientific literature.

As we know, culture is one of the most complex, multifaceted, and diverse social phenomena. [2,3] The word “*culture*” originates from the Latin *colere*, but in the 18th and 19th centuries this term also began to be applied to people. Accordingly, if a person stood out with refined taste, good manners, and erudition (for example, students in our society who have read many books and sources), he or she was considered “*cultured*.” At that time, the term was mostly applied to nobles (aristocrats) to distinguish them from “uncultured” people. In German, the word “*Kultur*” conveyed the meaning of a high degree of civilization.

Discussion

The concept of “*information*” (from the Latin *informatio* — message, explanation, presentation) is common to all separate sciences, and the information approach, which encompasses a set of ideas, has become a universal scientific concept. In the dictionary of education and pedagogy, “information” is explained as one of the general concepts of science. Specialists emphasize that in pedagogy and psychology, the term “information” is used to describe any content of a message, as well as any data considered from the perspective of its transmission in time and space.

In contemporary linguistics, however, the term “*semantic information*” is used to denote information that has a certain meaning and can be understood and interpreted in the process of human communication. The semantic characteristic of information demonstrates the possibility of interpreting it through language (texts, drawings, photographs, magnetic recordings, gestures and facial expressions, smell and taste sensations; or chromosomes that transmit genetic information).

Culture (from the Latin *cultura* - education, training, development) is the set of practical, material, and spiritual achievements of society, reflecting the historically attained level of development of society and humanity. In a narrow sense, culture is a sphere of society’s spiritual life, which primarily includes the system of education, upbringing, and creative activity, as well as institutions and organizations (schools, institutes, clubs, museums, theaters, creative associations, society, and others) that ensure their functioning.

In the modern professional education dictionary, culture is defined as the level of people’s education, upbringing, and mastery of a particular field of knowledge or type of activity. [4] The development of education on the basis of modern requirements demands fundamental changes and new approaches. Therefore, finding ways and opportunities for the effective use of information is considered one of the important tasks of education. This should teach learners not only to assimilate and process information, to create its imitations, but also to produce new information based on new ideas, integrate acquired information, and thereby improve their competence in using information in both educational and life activities.

In many cases, the amount of assimilated information is considered a measure of the effectiveness of education, and in assessing educational outcomes, the volume of acquired information is taken into account. However, it should be emphasized that the main requirement of the information society is determined not by the amount of acquired information, but by the ability to apply this information in specific fields and in the course of life activities. A number of scientific studies also emphasize that in competence-based education, importance should be attached to educational outcomes, where the focus should be not on the volume of information acquired by the learner, but on the ability to apply this information in various situations. [5]

The scope of information use determines the level of social development.

According to UNESCO’s conclusion, *informatization* is the widespread use of means for collecting, storing, and transmitting information. It ensures the systematization of existing

knowledge, the formation and management of new knowledge, as well as its further improvement and development. The term *information* is applied in all spheres of human society, and on its basis, the processes of education and upbringing are carried out, as well as pedagogical activities are managed. Information acquires a certain level of importance in social life, particularly as a primary source in managing educational processes, because it provides wide opportunities to divide information obtained from an object into systems and parts, to process it, and to apply algorithms for transmitting it according to specific purposes. [7] Education constantly performs the task of forming and developing students' skills in acquiring and processing information. The growth in learners' mastery of information and the expansion of its usage scope serve as indicators in determining the effectiveness of education.

The consistent modernization of the entire educational system is connected with the general trends of global development, one of which requires the transition to a post-industrial and information-based society. The main stage of this transition involves not only the active use of computer technologies in the learning process but also informatization of education, which includes the integration of information and communication technologies into educational and upbringing processes, the informatization of educational institutions and the management of the education system, and the creation of infrastructure that ensures the informatization process.

Currently, information technologies play a crucial role in social development worldwide, and the general level of a state and a nation's information culture determines its socio-economic position in the world community. The transformation of information into one of the most important universal categories reflects the objective need for information resources in all types of human activity education, research, and production. [6]

Information, as a material, possesses its own unique characteristics. Firstly, it is indestructible and inexhaustible. When information is used (applied), it does not diminish, and it creates a tradition of becoming common human property. Secondly, information lacks a universal measure. All attempts to measure the amount of information are tied to conditional measures, depending on the specific situation and the specific recipient of the message. [8]

Thirdly, unlike human or material resources, information resources possess only potential (probabilistic) value; they are not independent and, on their own, cannot dynamically develop a social system. Clearly, the value of information depends heavily on the method of obtaining it and the specific situation in which it is applied, and effectiveness is achieved accordingly.

Conclusion. It is no coincidence that the 21st century is associated with informatization and the formation of an information society, as these are considered processes of effectively developing humanity's accumulated information resources. Recognizing that it is impossible to successfully solve serious economic, social, or technical problems without processing a certain amount of information is a defining feature of the information society.

The information society is a civilization based on development and existence (functioning) that relies on special data, conditionally called *information*, which possesses the property of connecting a person's spiritual and material world.

On one hand, through its role as innovative technologies and computer programs, information constitutes the material environment of human life. On the other hand, it serves as the main means of interpersonal relations, which always arise, change in form and content, and transfer from one person to another.

In other words, information simultaneously defines both the socio-cultural life and the material existence of human beings.

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